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Relationships among Academic Delay of Gratification, Motivated Learning Strategies, and Academic Grit in Manila City Medical Students

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Abstract

To become a physician, one must invest a significant amount of time and resist immediate gratification for something more rewarding and fulfilling in the future. Additionally, being in medical school also requires perseverance and effective study habits. Therefore, medical students are familiar with Academic Delay of Gratification (ADOG), Academic Grit (AG), and Motivated Strategies for Learning (MSL) as it helps them to be successful in their studies and future careers. To understand the relationship between the three aforementioned variables, this study aimed to investigate the levels of medical students in Manila City in terms of their ADOG, AG, and MSL. In order to do so, survey-questionnaires were provided to the 121 medical students who were selected using a purposive sampling technique in this correlational quantitative research design. Based on the descriptive statistics, most medical students were shown to have high levels of ADOG, high levels of MSL domains (except Test Anxiety), and moderate to high levels of AG. Moreover, Spearman's Rho analysis revealed that ADOG and MSL domains have a weak but statistically significant positive correlation, except self-regulation which had moderate positive correlation. A significant relationship but weak positive correlation was also found between ADOG and AG. Meanwhile, results showed a significant moderate to strong positive correlation between AG and MSL domains except test anxiety. Findings from the current research therefore emphasize the notion that self-regulation, a key component of the "cool" cognitive system in the CAPS Theory, is crucial for enhancing ADOG, MSL, and AG among medical students.

Keywords: *academic delay of gratification, motivated strategies for learning, academic grit, medical students, cognitive-affective processing system theory*

Introduction

Becoming a physician requires a significant investment of time and hard work in exchange for the ultimate reward of a fulfilling career in the healthcare field. Furthermore, medical school itself can be seen as a "marshmallow test" where students must resist the temptation of immediate gratification, such as socializing or pursuing other interests, in favor of their long-term academic and professional goals (Abadilla, 2018). Therefore, medical students are familiar with delayed gratification, specifically Academic Delay of Gratification (ADOG). This concept emphasizes the importance of choosing future benefits over immediate rewards within academic contexts (Bembenuity & Karabenick, 2013; Abd-El-Fattah & Salman, 2017). Moreover, ADOG does not only influence students' academic achievements (Rahardi & Dartanto, 2021) but also plays a crucial role in shaping medical students' approaches to motivated strategies for learning and academic grit (Souza et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2023), which are essential for their success in their studies and future careers.

Research has consistently shown that medical education is characterized by high levels of academic rigor and demands, which necessitate resilience, perseverance, and effective study habits (De Oliveira et al, 2017; Nair et al, 2023). Understanding how these factors interrelate provides valuable insights into the factors that contribute to success in medical school and beyond. This study also applies the Cognitive-Affective Processing System (CAPS) Theory and its hot/cool systems paradigm to explore these dynamics, specifically focusing on academic delay of gratification (ADOG) in medical students. (Mischel & Shoda, 1995). In 1999, Mischel's work along with his colleague, Metcalfe, introduced a paradigm that serves as a bridge under the two concepts of CAPS and ADOG—the hot/cool system. It is a proposed framework consisting of two systems that aids the dilemma of how cognitive processes perform. In short, there are two centers of decision making that influences an individuals' actions (Chakraborty, 2017a). First is the cool 'cognitive' system, also known as the "know" system, which indicates emotionally neutral, contemplative, slow, strategic, and is the center for self-control and self-regulation. Then the hot 'emotional' system, commonly called the "go" system, which refers to the impulsive, fear, reflexive, fast, and is the basis of emotionality. It must also be noted that both of these systems work interconnectedly (Metcalfe & Mischel, 1999; Mischel & Ayduk, 2010). For medical students, the ability to regulate these systems is crucial for managing both immediate academic demands and longer-term goals.

By applying this framework, the study aims to clarify how CAPS affect students' academic delay of gratification. This approach links directly to the research questions, examining how medical students' motivation, learning strategies (such as intrinsic value, self-efficacy, test anxiety, and self-regulation), and academic grit contribute to their capacity for delaying gratification. These factors, shaped by the balance between hot and cool systems, are essential for understanding the self-regulatory processes that medical students employ to succeed in high-stakes environments.

Research Questions

This study addressed the following questions:

1. What is the level of Academic Delay of Gratification among the respondents?
2. What is the level of Motivated Strategies for Learning among the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1. intrinsic value;
 - 2.2. self-efficacy;
 - 2.3. test anxiety;
 - 2.4. cognitive strategy use; and
 - 2.5. self-regulation?
3. What is the level of Academic Grit among the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between Academic Delay of Gratification and Motivated Strategies for Learning?
5. Is there a significant relationship between Academic Delay of Gratification and Academic Grit?
6. Is there a significant relationship between Motivated Strategies for Learning and Academic Grit?

Literature Review

Walter Mischel's CAPS Theory and the famous "Marshmallow Test" laid the groundwork for understanding the significance and implications of delayed gratification in various life domains such as health, finances, and relationships, most particularly, in career and academia (Dingess & Wilt, 2020; Peake, 2017; Watts et al., 2018; Carlson et al., 2018). In medical education, where students must navigate complex and prolonged academic journeys, the capacity to delay immediate rewards for the sake of achieving long-term career goals is especially vital.

The ability to delay gratification is a key cognitive trait that involves resisting immediate temptations in pursuit of future goals. In the context of medical education, ADOG is critical for students who face years of rigorous academic training, including long hours of study, clinical practice, and exams. ADOG has been linked to better academic outcomes, as it helps students maintain focus on long-term professional objectives, such as becoming competent physicians, rather than yielding to the distractions of short-term rewards (Souza et al., 2018). Research also shows that students with high ADOG tend to use more effective learning strategies, better manage their time, and exhibit persistence in the face of academic challenges, all of which are essential in the demanding field of medical education.

Motivated Strategies for Learning (MSL) refer to a set of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral strategies that students employ to manage their learning effectively. The primary components of MSL are intrinsic value, self-efficacy, test anxiety, cognitive strategy use, and self-regulation. These strategies have been found to significantly impact students' academic performance, particularly in high-pressure environments like medical education. As suggested by recent studies, MSL is essential in fostering academic achievement, with motivation playing a central role in guiding the use of effective learning strategies (Bliss & Jacobson, 2020; Guo et al., 2023).

Furthermore, academic grit (AG), defined as the perseverance and passion for long-term goals, has been identified as a key non-cognitive skill that correlates positively with motivation and self-regulated learning (Bliss & Jacobson, 2020). Medical students, in particular, are required to show resilience in high-pressure environments where failure is common, and success requires dedication to continuous learning. Research by Rusli et al. (2020) suggests that medical students, even when facing challenges, often view setbacks as opportunities for growth rather than deterrents. AG is strongly correlated with intrinsic motivation, and this intrinsic drive helps medical students maintain their passion and commitment throughout their academic careers. Moreover, AG enhances students' ability to persist in their studies, even during difficult times, aligning closely with ADOG.

As students with high ADOG are more likely to delay immediate rewards in favor of long-term goals, their ability to engage in cognitive strategy use becomes more pronounced, leading them to employ more effective study habits and enhance their academic performance (Souza et al., 2018). The self-regulation component of MSL, which involves goal-setting and self-monitoring, aligns closely with ADOG as students must self-manage their academic progress over long periods, like the years required for medical education. Furthermore,

self-efficacy—the belief in one's capability to succeed—strengthens both ADOG and AG, as confident students are more likely to persist through setbacks and maintain the drive necessary to achieve long-term academic goals. This belief in one's ability to succeed fuels AG, because students with high self-efficacy are less likely to be deterred by failures and are more motivated to use cognitive strategies to overcome academic challenges (Guo et al., 2023; Bliss & Jacobson, 2020). Additionally, intrinsic value—the enjoyment and personal satisfaction students derive from learning—serves as a foundation for AG, providing students with the internal motivation to continue their studies despite difficulties. Notably, test anxiety can impact students' motivation and performance, but students with higher AG and better self-regulation are more likely to manage anxiety effectively, allowing them to stay focused on long-term goals (Xiao et al., 2021).

The integration of academic delay of gratification (ADOG), motivated strategies for learning (MSL), and academic grit (AG) is vital for success in medical education. By fostering these components, medical schools can support students in developing the resilience, perseverance, and motivation needed to thrive in the medical field. However, despite significant findings in related research, gaps remain in understanding how these factors interact specifically in the context of medical education. This study seeks to explore the relationships of ADOG, MSL and academic grit in medical students, addressing the gaps in current literature and offering insights that

may benefit educational practices in medical training.

Methodology

Respondents

This study utilized a purposive sampling technique, a strategic, intentional, non-probability sampling approach to ensure representation from specific year levels and pre-med backgrounds, which were best suited to address and gather in-depth data related to the research objectives. The sample consisted of 121 medical students who graduated with bachelor's degrees or participated in a medical accelerated program, are currently enrolled in medical school in Manila City, and are from Year Level 1 to 3. Out of 121 respondents, the medical students' ages ranged from 18-29, wherein 35 were 24 years old and the youngest was 18 years old. The sample included 57 female and 64 male respondents. Meanwhile, the pre-med courses taken by most of the respondents were BS Medical Technology with 33 respondents followed by BS Biology with 25 respondents. In addition, several respondents took accelerated programs such as LEAPmed or BS Basic Human Studies with 19 respondents, and INTARmed or BS Basic Medical Sciences with 2 respondents. Furthermore, most respondents were in Year Level 2 (YL2) with 58 respondents followed by YL1 with 43 respondents, and YL3 with 20 respondents. By selecting medical students in Year Levels 1 to 3, this study targeted those in the foundational academic phase of medical education, which typically spans the first three years before entering their clinical clerkship phase. Meanwhile, their pre-med backgrounds provide insight into how various foundations influence students' acclimatization in medical school.

Instrument

Academic Delay of Gratification Scale (ADOGS)

The Academic Delay of Gratification Scale (ADOGS) is a 10-items self-report questionnaire that was developed by Bembenuity and Karabenick (1998a) that helps us to measure the students' ability to delay immediate rewards in an academic setting. The scale is a 4-point Likert scale with two reverse-coded items that showed an acceptable internal consistency across different studies and a high construct validity when adopted to the Filipino population (Ganotice & King, 2014;

Abd-El-Fattah & Salman, 2017). Multiple studies showed that the scale's Cronbach alpha regularly falls between $\alpha = .70$ and $\alpha = .84$ (Bembenuity, 2007; Bembenuity & Karabenick, 2004; Chakraborty, 2017b; Ganie, 2020; Zhao et al., 2023). In this study, the Cronbach alpha for ADOGS reported at $\alpha = .583$.

Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaires (MSLQ) The Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ) was developed from 1982 to 1991 by Pintrich and his colleagues in the National Center for Research to Improve Postsecondary Teaching and Learning (NCRIPTAL) and was developed to measure college students' motivational orientations and their use of various learning strategies (Pintrich et al., 1991, 1993; Iwamoto et al., 2017). The MSLQ was a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (not at all true of me) to 7 (very true of me) with reverse items and was originally 81-item but was developed to a simpler version consisting of 44-item with two components: Motivation—consisting of intrinsic, self-efficacy, and test anxiety—and Learning Strategies—consisting of cognitive strategy used and self-regulation. Studies assessed the questionnaires using Cronbach alpha that indicate a high internal consistency value across the subscales ranging from $\alpha = .74$ and $\alpha = .89$ (Iwamoto et al., 2017). In this study, the Cronbach alpha for MSLQ in each subscales were ranging from $\alpha = .658$ and $\alpha = .922$.

Academic Grit Scale (AGS)

The Academic Grit Scale by Clark and Malecki (2019) was a novel self-report questionnaire that consists of 10 items and measures the participants' perseverance and passion for long-term academic goals. The scale is a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (not at all like me) to 5 (very much like me). The AGS was tested for its internal consistency reliability and was reported to have a Cronbach alpha of .918 (Clark, 2017). In this study, the Cronbach alpha reported were at $\alpha = .886$.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *The Level of Academic Delay Gratification (ADOG) among Medical Students*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
ADOG	3.23	0.389	High

The mean score of 3.23 from Table 1 indicates that medical students in Manila City exhibit a high level of ADOG, signifying that they have high tendencies to postpone immediate rewards in favor of their long-term academic goals. Furthermore, the low standard deviation of 0.389 suggests consistent scores among the respondents in terms of their ability to delay gratification. This consistency of data aligns with the studies by Bembenuity (2021) and McGarry & Corwyn (2022), supporting the notion that medical students delay personal gratifications to focus on their demanding academic commitments. Meanwhile, Shields (2019) found similar trends, noting that medical students prioritize academic responsibilities over personal life; and Bransen et al. (2019) who also highlighted the necessity of self-regulatory behaviors in the medical field's complex environment. This data then suggests that when one exhibits ADOG, they simply put their priorities to push through medical school first, then the other domains of their social life second. It is common

knowledge that medical school is very expensive and some people cannot afford to fail. Due to the complex and advanced study of medicine among medical students, instead of partying out with friends and skipping classes, there are more chances that they will rather study for the practical exam tomorrow and spend the night inside a library, than spend the night outside and getting a lower grade because they crammed. Therefore, the high levels of ADOG among medical students may stem from their significant investment of time and effort, their awareness of the consequences of failing, and their personal goal of becoming medical degree (MD) holders. Thus, medical students' ability to delay gratification reflects their priorities and self-discipline in navigating the challenges of medical education, underscoring the importance of long-term goals over immediate impulses.

Table 2. *The Levels of Motivated Strategies for Learning (MSL) among Medical Students*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
MSL	5.75	0.873	High
Motivation: Intrinsic			
MSL	4.73	1.007	High
Motivation: Self-efficacy			
MSL	3.8	1.418	Low
Motivation: Test Anxiety			
MSL	5.32	0.755	High
Learning Strategy: Cognitive Strategy Use			
MSL	5.02	0.783	High
Learning Strategy: Self-regulation			

Through the responses garnered from MSLQ, the descriptive statistics showed the means, standard deviations, and interpretations of the levels of the five domains of MSL among the participants, as illustrated in table 2.

The intrinsic subscale garnered a mean score of 5.75, indicating high intrinsic value among participants, with a standard deviation of 0.873 suggesting low variability. This finding aligns with studies by Farooq et al. (2018) and Wu et al. (2020), which showed that medical students tend to have intrinsic value. These results suggest that most respondents in this study have found their personal calling in the medical field, driven not just by the prestige of the title but also by the altruistic desire to make a positive impact on the well-being of patients and the community.

In Wu and colleagues' (2020) study, intrinsic motivation was identified as a significant predictor of self-efficacy in academic performance. This could explain why participants in this study also reported high self-efficacy, with a mean score of 4.73. Despite the difficulty of medical education, a high level of self-efficacy suggests that students believe in their ability to succeed. However, with a standard deviation of 1.007, there was moderate variability in self-efficacy scores, indicating that while most scores were around the mean, there was some spread in participants' self-efficacy levels. This variability could be attributed to individual differences and backgrounds.

Furthermore, as stated by Klassen & Klassen (2018), high self-efficacy helps students approach exams with confidence and resilience, serving as a protective factor against test anxiety. Thus, the scores of self-efficacy usually contrasts with the scores on test anxiety. This could also be observed with the mean score of test anxiety which was 3.8, suggesting a lower range of anxiety levels among participants. However, the standard deviation of 1.418 indicated greater variability, meaning some participants experienced much higher or lower anxiety levels. This could be due to the state-dependent nature of test anxiety, influenced by situational factors like upcoming exams or individual attitudes toward academic pressure.

Meanwhile, the cognitive strategy use subscale presented a mean score of 5.32, indicating that medical students reported high usage of cognitive strategies. Practicing cognitive strategies, such as rehearsal, elaboration, and organization, impacts students' learning outcomes by helping them acquire and retain knowledge effectively (Souza et al., 2018). With a standard deviation of 0.755, the data points were relatively close to the mean, suggesting low to moderate variability. This implies that most participants consistently use cognitive strategies, reflecting the necessity for medical students to be diligent and systematic in their studies.

Lastly, the self-regulation subscale had a mean score of 5.02, indicating high levels of self-regulation among medical students. With a standard deviation of 0.783, the scores were proportionately close to the mean, showing moderate variability. Self-regulation allows students to set goals and monitor their progress, crucial for navigating the demanding medical education environment (Bransen, 2019; Ballouk et al., 2022). These findings emphasize the concept of Self-Regulated Learning (SRL), where self-regulated learners are proactive, aware of their academic development, and likely to persevere and achieve better results when faced with challenges (Wang, 2021).

Table 3. *The Level of Academic Grit (AG) among Medical Students*

	Mean	SD	Interpretation
AG	4.11	0.586	High

Table 3 illustrated that the level of AG among medical students was 4.11, which corresponds to the statement that the higher the mean score, the higher the participants' academic grit (Clark & Malecki, 2019). The result was consistent with the findings of Miller-Matero et al. (2018), which stated that most of the medical students showed a higher level of perseverance and were noted to be the average level amongst the students. Alzerwi (2020) stated that studying medicine is a long-term commitment that includes a goal-setting skill, time management skills, perseverance, and focus. This concluded that medical students who are high in academic grit were driven to invest time and effort due to the difficulty of lessons, examinations, and other requirements that challenged their knowledge. Particularly in medical schools where the terminologies and applications are more complicated that require a lot of effort and time to understand, and are harder to master than in bachelors degrees.

Table 4. Relationship between Academic Delay of Gratification (ADOG) and Motivated Strategies for Learning (MSL)

	ADOG	rho	p-value	decision
MSL Motivation: Intrinsic		0.141	0.124	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Motivation: Self-efficacy		0.157	0.086	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Motivation: Test Anxiety		0.165	0.071	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Learning Strategy: Cognitive Strategy Use		0.167	0.067	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Learning Strategy: Self-regulation		0.31	< .001	Reject H01

Note. $p < .05$

The correlation analysis between ADOG and MSL, presented in Table 4, showed that ADOG had a very weak positive correlation with four MSL domains: intrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, test anxiety, and cognitive strategy use, but a moderate positive correlation with the last MSL domain which is self-regulation.

Spearman's rho analysis indicated a very weak positive correlation between ADOG and intrinsic motivation ($r = 0.141$, $p = 0.124$), suggesting that while ADOG slightly increases intrinsic motivation, it is not significant enough to reject the null hypothesis. This contrasts with studies (Bembenuity, 2021; Chakraborty & Chechi, 2022; Zheng, 2021) suggesting that high ADOG enhances motivation, rather possibly due to the long duration of medical school which diminishes their perceived internal rewards over time. In short, other than the skills, knowledge, and compassion they gain, these medical students might start relying on external rewards like passing or achieving a higher grade that will help sustain their motivation.

Similarly, ADOG and self-efficacy had a very weak positive correlation ($r = 0.157$, $p = 0.086$), indicating that although there is a slight increase in self-efficacy with higher ADOG, it is not significant. This result is supported by Bembenuity (2002) wherein self-efficacy contributes to the willingness of the individual to delay their gratification (As cited by Zhao et al., 2023). Despite this weak correlation supporting that self-efficacy contributes to delaying gratification, the variability in self-efficacy among medical students explains the non-significant relationship whereas regardless of how high or low their self-efficacy, medical students may still have tendencies to delay immediate gratification.

The correlation between ADOG and test anxiety was also very weak ($r = 0.165$, $p = 0.071$), suggesting a slight increase in test anxiety with higher ADOG. This weak correlation aligns with findings of Jiao and his colleagues (2022) that students with less anxiety had a negative correlation with ADOG; thus, indicating that students experience varied levels of anxiety regardless of their tendency to delay gratification due to factors like academic performance and personal pressures.

ADOG and cognitive strategy use revealed a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.167$, $p = 0.067$), indicating a slight increase in cognitive strategy use with higher ADOG, but not significantly. This finding—contrary to some studies (Bembenuity, 2021; Chakraborty & Chechi, 2022; Zheng, 2021) which states that students who have ADOG tend to be engaged in proactive learning behaviors that exhibit cognitive strategy use—may be due to individual differences in cognitive strategies based on personal preferences, learning styles, and prior experiences. Some of these medical students may excel in using cognitive strategies regardless of their ADOG tendencies, while others may still struggle.

Lastly, ADOG and self-regulation showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.31$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher ADOG is significantly associated with better self-regulation. This finding suggests that medical students who were better at delaying gratification were likely to have higher levels of self-regulation, which were essential for effective learning. This result is thereby supported by the idea that delay of gratification was related with self-regulation (Bembenuity & Karabenick, 1998a, 1998b; As cited by McGarry and Corwyn, 2022). From the gathered data, the researchers can safely assume that highly self-regulated individuals are better at managing emotions which helps them to resist immediate temptations and maintain focus on long-term goals. This emotional regulation enables them to delay gratification and make more rational decisions which conform to the paradigm under the CAPS Theory, specifically the

“cool” system.

Table 5. *Relationship between Academic Delay of Gratification (ADOG) and Academic Grit (AG)*

<i>ADOG</i>	<i>rho</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>decision</i>
AG	0.216	0.017	Reject H02

Note. $p < .05$

Table 5 showed that ADOG and AG have a weak positive correlation of 0.216. Moreover, since the p-value ($p = 0.017$) was less than the common significance level of 0.05, the correlation was considered statistically significant and enough to reject the null hypothesis (H02) that stated that there was no significant relationship between ADOG and AG. Medical education alone is not easy, and while applying ADOG can be rewarding at the end—it could still make the journey of a medical student more challenging. This is where AG comes in as an aid, as it acts as a behavioral determinant of cognitive-affective units in resisting immediate gratification in pursuit of distant goals (Armstrong et al., 2018; Balakrishnan, 2020). In simple words, the more grit a student has, the more likely they are to postpone their leisure activities in order to focus on achieving long-term goals that they themselves consider to be very important.

Table 6. *Relationship between Motivated Strategies for Learning (MSL) and Academic Grit (AG)*

<i>ADOG</i>	<i>rho</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>decision</i>
MSL Motivation: Intrinsic	0.506	< .001	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Motivation: Self-efficacy	0.436	< .001	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Motivation: Test Anxiety	-0.076	0.406	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Learning Strategy: Cognitive Strategy Use	0.574	< .001	Failed to Reject H01
MSL Learning Strategy: Self-regulation	0.618	< .001	Reject H01

Note. $p < .05$

The results of correlation between MSL and AG showed a positive correlation with the domains of MSL including: intrinsic, self-efficacy, cognitive strategy used, and self-regulation. The only domain that failed to reject the null hypothesis is test anxiety.

The reported data in intrinsic value subscale in MSL corresponded with $r = 0.506$, indicating that it had a strong positive correlation with AG, which determined that when intrinsic increases, AG also increases. This signified that medical students who were gritty to achieve their academic goals are more likely intrinsically motivated (Komarraju et al., 2009; As cited by Mirza et al., 2021). This suggested that medical students who were intrinsically motivated by the idea of studying in medical schools, attaining the MD in their name, saving lives, curing diseases, and helping citizens and families achieve a better quality of life, are more likely to maintain their focus and are gritty enough to achieve their goals.

In self-efficacy subscale, it was reported to have a $r = 0.436$ which corresponded that self-efficacy and AG have a moderate positive correlation. The result determined that when self-efficacy increased, the AG as well increased. This suggested that medical students who were gritty also tend to believe in their capabilities that they can manage challenges and perform well in medical schools (Klassen & Klassen, 2018). Specifically when committing to enrolling in a medical school, one must effectively think that they have what it takes to survive. In addition, since medical school is challenging and difficult, medical students who believe in their capabilities and beliefs that they can succeed in medical school, are likely to have passion and perseverance in achieving their goals.

On the contrary, test anxiety was reported to have a very weak and negative correlation with AG ($r = -0.076$), which determined that when test anxiety decreased, the AG increased. The results concluded that the data could be due to numerous factors such as academic achievements and failures, parents' perceptions and attitudes toward it, GPA and many more. A good example for this subscale would be when taking the National Medical Admission Test (NMAT) and acquiring one's percentile rank (PR). It does not directly mean that once they have successfully passed and enrolled in a medical school of their choice, that they would flourish immediately after. Studies also linked the fact that the nature of test anxiety and self-efficacy were usually contrasted with one another (Klassen & Klassen, 2018; Javed et al., 2022), and so with that logic, if there existed a significant relationship between medical students' high self-efficacy and high AG, then their test anxiety was expected to decrease and not increase—manifesting a negative correlation like the table implied.

Another subscale that was reported to have a strong positive correlation is cognitive strategy used with 0.574. The result suggested that medical students who have high cognitive strategy use means they choose their strategies, battles amidst medical school, maximizing their way of learning, and using their resources and knowledge wisely. This implied that students have individual differences in terms of perseverance effort they provide and strategy used (Jiang et al., 2021). In short, to successfully thrive in a competitive environment, a medical student is anticipated to have his/her own cognitive strategies that will help them perform more efficiently and effectively thereby helping them to remain and persist in medical school.

Lastly, the self-regulation subscale was also reported to have a strong positive correlation with AG ($r = 0.618$) which meant that when self-regulation increases, AG also increases. The result supported several studies which suggested that: students with high grit are engaged with effective learning strategies (Angela et al., 2020), grit as a predictor of SLR (Guo et al., 2023), and self-regulated students are more persistent (Zusho, 2017; Wang and Guan, 2020; As cited by Wang, 2021). Usually, AG exists because there is a goal that they perceive to be very significant in their life, and that is one of many reasons why medical students continue persevering in spite of many downfalls they may encounter in medical school. Understanding how to achieve those goals is just as important as making sure they persist regardless of the struggles. Without self-regulation, these long-term goals would seem clouded and hindered by the idea that their goal is too far away from what is in the present. As a result, medical students that do not practice both AG and self-regulation may fall short in one way or another. This signifies that students in the present study have a high self-regulation that helps them to carry on and achieve their long-term goals.

In summary, the findings of this study highlighted some significant challenges faced by medical students, particularly in managing their tendencies for academic delay of gratification (ADOG), use of effective learning strategies and developing grit, which are essential for academic success. Therefore, to support these medical students in keeping up with the demands of medical education, implementing tailored support systems—such as academic counseling, goal-setting programs, and resilience-building workshops—could help medical students enhance self-regulation learning strategies and grit, thereby better supporting the students' persistence and academic success in the demanding medical field. Given that the current study focuses on Manila-based medical students, comparing these findings with those from medical schools in other countries could illuminate how different educational approaches shape students' motivation, grit, and self-regulation. Such comparative studies might reveal differences in ADOG, MSL, and AG based on varied pedagogical approaches, aiding in the development of supportive practices for medical students worldwide. While these findings apply specifically to medical students in Manila, it is possible that similar academic pressures exist in medical schools for other regions worldwide. For example, intrinsic motivation, as well as the need for high levels of grit and self-regulation, may be prevalent among medical students in various places facing high academic demands like in China (Jiang et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2024), Israel, and Japan (Meo et al., 2019). Future studies could explore these dimensions in diverse cultural and geographical settings, allowing for comparisons that reveal both universal and culturally specific patterns in the way medical students approach academic challenges.

As previously mentioned, while the findings offer valuable insights, the sample's geographical and cultural specificity limits the generalizability to other regions. Additionally, variability in factors like test anxiety suggests that personal and situational factors affect how students manage stress in medical education. Future researchers could address these limitations by expanding to a larger and more diverse sample and by investigating additional individual and contextual factors that may influence students' learning strategies and ADOG.

Conclusions

Based on the analyzed data, several conclusions can be drawn. ADOG exhibited insignificant but weak positive correlations with four out of five MSL domains. Self-regulation was the only MSL domain that reached statistical significance and had a strong positive correlation with ADOG in the present study, suggesting further research needed to explore why this relationship is stronger than with other MSL domains. Thus, these findings indicated that ADOG plays a crucial role in self-regulated learning. It also highlighted that while ADOG significantly influences self-regulation, it does not substantially affect other MSL domains, suggesting that the cool cognitive system of self-regulation is pivotal for medical students in managing their emotions and maintaining focus on long-term goals. Conversely, ADOG showed a weaker yet statistically significant correlation with AG, indicating that students who can delay gratification tend to exhibit higher levels of perseverance in pursuing long-term academic goals. This result implied that grit somehow acts as a predictor to self-regulatory behavior in delaying immediate rewards which is one of the indicators that tell whether the individual used the cool system in CAPS theory. Lastly, AG demonstrated strong positive correlations and a significant relationship between AG and four MSL domains which supports the idea that motivational strategies are interconnected with grit, emphasizing the importance of integrating these strategies into psychological and educational practices to foster perseverance and passion among medical students. These conclusions were consistent with CAPS theory, which posited that cognitive-affective units interact to shape behavior, highlighting how the "cool" cognitive system enhances ADOG, MSL, and AG. However, the lack of significant correlations with the MSL domain—test anxiety suggests that addressing test anxiety may require separate emotional-focused interventions that will target the cognitive and emotional aspects of the individuals, which is emotion centered on the "hot" cognitive system, highlighting that individuals may experience negative self-thoughts and heightened emotional responses triggered by the stress of upcoming or current academic examination that also contributes to a smaller size of population. For example, medical students may have heightened responses that can impact focus and performance, making it particularly challenging to apply ADOG effectively. Therefore, in addition to CAPS, interventions rooted in anxiety-reduction techniques—such as cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) or mindfulness practices—could provide valuable support by helping students manage the emotional intensity of test anxiety and develop healthier coping mechanisms for high-stakes assessments.

Practical implications include integrating motivational strategies into educational practices to enhance AG and ADOG, as well as developing the aforementioned targeted interventions for test anxiety. By leveraging insights from CAPS theory, psychologists can design comprehensive support programs that promote both cognitive and affective dimensions crucial for medical students' success in rigorous academic settings. Further research is also needed to explore specific factors influencing variations in ADOG among medical

students, investigate the effects of ADOG on individuals, and examine the specific cognitive strategies and contextual factors that contribute to high levels of MSL, AG, and the impact of test anxiety on academic performance. Finally, the recent study limits the researchers to gather a larger sample size due to the factor that the participants are from a narrow locale. With that, future researchers could also consider increasing sample sizes, broadening research locales, coordinating with universities, exploring the accelerated programs' impact on the aforementioned variables, and examining the confounding variables that may have affected the results of the study such as demographic profile, academic performance, social environment, GPA, and learning styles. These recommendations could help the future researchers gauge the reliability of the data and ensure that participants were in the same state and place while answering the questionnaires.

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